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INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR ESTABLISHING PARTNERSHIPS AND RELATIONS BETWEEN STAKEHOLDERS – PERSONS RESPONSIBLE FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNATIONAL LEGAL STANDARDS IN THE FIELD OF HIGHER EDUCATION AT THE NATIONAL AND INSTITUTIONAL LEVELS

Zukay Zh.

*L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University
Astana, Senior Lecturer, Master of Laws*

Kulikpayeva M.

*Institute of Legislation and Legal Information of the Republic of Kazakhstan
Astana, Head of Department of International Law and Comparative Studies, PhD*

ABSTRACT

The World Declaration on Higher Education for the 21st century: vision and action (Paris, October 9, 1998) in Article 17 draws attention to the importance of partnerships and alliances. What is meant is that change management focuses on partnerships and connections between stakeholders, namely policy makers at national and institutional levels; teachers; researchers; students; administrative and technical staff of higher education institutions; community groups, etc. Thus, partnership is built on the basis of common interests, mutual respect, and trust. Such interaction acts as a locomotive for renewal and further development of higher education. Moreover, any cooperation is based on and regulated by both international and national legal standards.

This article will consider not only international legal treaties (as a basis for establishing partnerships), but also the direct participation of the Republic of Kazakhstan in these treaties, as well as its national legal legislation in the field of higher education.

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Keywords: Paris Declaration, higher education, partnership, international law, national legislation, Republic of Kazakhstan, standards, responsible parties.

Introduction.

The dynamic development of global processes has a direct impact on the sphere of education, regardless of its level (stage). Nowadays, any state strives to build an education system in accordance with its political and economic development; adhere to advanced international quality standards, introducing them into its domestic legislation.

As it is known, higher education institutions in most developed countries have very broad autonomy in matters of establishing and organizing various forms of cooperation with foreign partner universities and in organizing international exchanges. Supporting a certain legal status, they have clearly established rules for conducting business, including foreign economic activity [1, p.128].

The field of higher education is quite complex and, at the same time, unique. On the one hand, higher education presupposes the training of a highly qualified and competitive specialist in his field. On the other hand, this is a certain cycle from the point of view of the organization of the educational process, which involves a number of interested parties: government agencies; teaching staff, researchers, students; administrative staff; representatives of the public.

All these stakeholders are able to manage and influence the educational sphere both independently and by interacting with each other. At the same time, any of their participation (in a personal capacity or jointly)

will always be subject to a certain legal order of international and/or national norms. And, if at the international level the basis of interaction is the relevant treaties and agreements, then the domestic level is built within the framework of national laws, decrees, strategic and program documents, etc.

International legal framework for establishing partnerships and relationships between stakeholders.

International Bill of Human Rights. When speaking about international legal standards, in our opinion, first of all, it is necessary to start with the International Bill of Human Rights, which consists of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966, and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966.

Thus, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948 (hereinafter referred to as UDHR) in Article 26 grants every person the right to education. This refers to free primary and secondary education. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and *higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit*. An important aspect is that education should be directed to the full development of the human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. Education shall promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups,

and shall further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace [2].

Another document, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966 (hereinafter referred to as ICCPR), does not contain specific provisions regarding education issues, since they fall within the scope of regulation of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966. However, the Preamble to this Covenant refers to the ideal of a free human being, which can only be realized if conditions are created under which everyone can enjoy his economic, social and cultural rights, as well as his civil and political rights [3].

Finally, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966 (hereinafter referred to as ICESCR) *imposes on States Parties the obligation to recognize the right of everyone to education.*

The States Parties to this Covenant recognize that, with a view to fully realizing this right, *higher education must be made equally accessible to all, on the basis of capacity, by every appropriate means, and in particular by the progressive introduction of free education (Article 13 ICESCR).*

In this regard, the following key principles should be followed:

- education should be directed to the full development of the human personality and the building of its dignity and should strengthen respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms;

- education shall enable all people to participate effectively in a free society, promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations and all racial, ethnic or religious groups, and further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace [4].

Thus, the three above-mentioned documents that make up the International Bill of Human Rights are the gold standard in ensuring the right to education and its accessibility to everyone without any discrimination. And that is most importantly, they impose certain obligations on member states to ensure the right to education.

Multilateral (regional) and bilateral international treaties. The key basis for establishing partnerships are international treaties or agreements concluded between states and/or interested parties in the field of higher education. There the parties determine the procedure for interaction, as well as the main types, forms, and areas of cooperation.

One of the striking examples of multilateral cooperation, which simultaneously covers not only states, but also directly higher education institutions (administrative and technical staff, teachers, students, researchers, etc.) is the creation of a model of network universities (the so-called “dual degree programs”).

Network University CIS. In 2008, the Russian side, with the support of the Interstate Fund for Humanitarian Cooperation of the CIS Member States (IFHC), initiated the project “Creation of the CIS Network University” in order to further develop humanitarian cooperation between the CIS member states. On June 11, 2009, the Agreement on the Consortium for the creation of the Network University of the Commonwealth

of Independent States (herein after – NU CIS) was signed.

The CIS Network University is an equal cooperation of higher educational institutions of the Commonwealth in the field of higher education, carried out in the format of a Consortium of Educational Organizations.

The main objective of the creation of the Consortium is to establish the CIS SU as a system of inter-university cooperation aimed at solving the following tasks:

- development of a single (common) educational space of universities of the member states of the Commonwealth of Independent States through the implementation of joint educational programs, the organization of “inclusive learning”, and new forms of inter-university cooperation;

- creation of mechanisms for the development of academic mobility of students and teachers within the Commonwealth of Independent States;

- promotion of intercultural dialogue among students, preservation, development and mutual enrichment of the culture, languages, historical and national traditions of the peoples of the member states of the Commonwealth of Independent States.

The Consortium includes more than 30 leading universities of the CIS member states: the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Republic of Armenia, the Republic of Belarus, the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic, the Republic of Moldova, the Russian Federation, the Republic of Tajikistan [5].

SCO University. On September 6, 2017, in Astana, the countries signed the *Agreement on the Establishment and Functioning of the University of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization*. The initiative to create the SCO University (herein after – Shanghai Cooperation Organization) was supported by the SCO member states of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the People's Republic of China, the Republic of Kyrgyzstan, and the Republic of Tajikistan.

The SCO University is a network of head (base) universities of the SCO member states with a coordinated educational program.

The main mission of the University of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization is to carry out joint training of highly qualified personnel, based on agreed innovative educational programs in specialties that are of priority interest for the economic and social development of the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization.

The main tasks of the SCO University include:

- Maintaining a unified educational space and integration trends.

- Expanding the exchange of students, postgraduates, doctoral students and scientific and pedagogical staff.

- Expansion of scientific and academic cooperation.

- Introduction of modern educational methods and technologies.

- Conducting examinations and developing recommendations in specific areas of SCO cooperation.

• Training of personnel for SCO structures and organizations affiliated with it [6].

It should be noted that the L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University (hereinafter referred to as ENU) implements 50 joint/dual-degree educational programs, including 3 bachelor's degree programs and 47 master's degree programs. L.N. Gumilyov ENU is a participant in both of the mentioned projects – the CIS SU and the SCO USHOS, where masters are trained in the areas of International Law, Economics, Tourism, Pedagogy and Psychology, etc.

Within the framework of the CIS SU and the SCO University, documents are submitted before the start of studies in the master's program. Mandatory requirements for admission through the CIS SU and the SCO University:

- be a 4th year undergraduate student and apply for a master's degree at ENU;
- have a bachelor's degree and apply for a master's degree at ENU [7].

In addition to the above-mentioned forms of multilateral cooperation, a large number of bilateral agreements have been concluded in the educational sphere. Using the example of the Republic of Kazakhstan, we can say that these are countries of various regions of the world - European, Asian, Turkic-speaking, etc.

The Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Government of the Republic of Turkey on cooperation in the field of education, concluded in Ankara on May 10, 2022, is aimed at developing cooperation in the field of education between the Parties in accordance with the national legislation of the states of the Parties and international treaties to which their states are parties, based on the principles of equality and mutual respect.

The key areas of cooperation include: exchange of experience in the field of education, implementation of educational programs, implementation of joint projects, encouragement of exchange of information and scientific publications; encouragement of exchange of teachers, experts, educators, heads of educational organizations and students; organization of advanced training programs for heads, teachers and employees in the field of education; exchange of experience in development and improvement of educational programs and materials; development of cooperation between educational institutions based on joint programs, partnerships and student activities, etc. [8].

The Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Government of the Kingdom of Spain on scientific and technical cooperation, concluded in Madrid on July 5, 2021, aims to develop scientific, technical and innovative cooperation between the two countries in the following forms:

- 1) participation of scientists from one Party in conferences, symposia, meetings held by the other Party;
- 2) conducting joint research projects in areas of interest to both Parties;
- 3) establishing contacts and links between universities, research centers, institutes and scientists of both countries;
- 4) exchange of scientific and technical delegations, individual scientists and specialists;

5) participation of scientists and research organizations of the public and private sectors in cooperation activities within the framework of this Agreement;

6) exchange of scientific and technical information and documentation, samples of products and materials, and technology transfer between the two countries;

7) any other forms of scientific and technical cooperation by agreement between the Parties and their research organizations[9].

The Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Government of the Republic of Lithuania on cooperation in the field of education, science, culture and art of October 6, 2011 establishes cooperation in the field of education and science through the exchange of information:

- about the education and science systems of their states;
- about the mutual recognition of educational documents between their states.

In addition, the Parties shall encourage the exchange of pupils, students, teachers, lecturers and scientists on the basis of concluding agreements between interested departments and organizations of the Parties or cooperation programs that define their rights, obligations and financial commitments.

Kazakhstan and Lithuania also support joint scientific projects, joint publications, publication of scientific papers and other forms of scientific cooperation envisaged by bilateral cooperation programs in the field of science and technology [10].

National legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan. According to the norms of the Constitution [11], Kazakhstan asserts itself as a democratic, secular, legal and social state, whose highest values are the individual, his life, rights and freedoms. Based on this, Article 30 of the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan guarantees compulsory secondary education in state educational institutions on a free basis. In addition, citizens have *the right to receive free higher education on a competitive basis in a state university. It is also allowed to receive paid education in private educational institutions on the grounds and in the manner established by law* [11].

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, higher education programs are aimed at training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the needs of economic sectors with the award of a bachelor's degree or the qualification of specialist. At the same time, the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated July 27, 2007 "On Education" grants educational organizations, in accordance with the specifics of their work, *the right to establish direct links with foreign educational, scientific and cultural organizations, international organizations and foundations, conclude bilateral and multilateral cooperation agreements, participate in international exchange programs for students, master's students, doctoral students, teachers and researchers, join international non-governmental organizations (associations) in the field of education* [12].

Article 29 of the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated February 18, 2011 "On Science" [13] determines that international cooperation is carried out on

the basis of relevant international treaties, international scientific, scientific and technical projects and programs, as well as in the form of assistance in establishing and expanding scientific and technical cooperation between Kazakhstani and foreign scientific and other organizations. Thus, *subjects of scientific and (or) scientific-technical activity have the right to join international scientific, scientific-technical organizations and associations, to participate in international scientific, scientific-technical projects and programs, scientific, scientific-technical projects and programs of foreign states.*

When speaking about public interest and its involvement in the field of education, one should refer to the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan “On Public Control”, which is intended to analyze and evaluate acts and decisions of public control objects for compliance with public interests.

Thus, according to Article 1 of this Law, objects of public control, along with others, include state institutions that are not state bodies, *autonomous educational organizations*, as well as other objects of public control provided for by the laws of the Republic of Kazakhstan. In this case, the subjects of public control may be citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan; non-profit organizations registered in the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan, with the exception of religious associations; other subjects that have been granted the authority to exercise public control in accordance with the laws of the Republic of Kazakhstan [14].

The above mentioned laws of the Republic of Kazakhstan indicate that they provide the right to establish foreign cooperation and involve in it the teaching staff, students, researchers, administrative and technical personnel.

At the same time, it is important to note that the coordination of the activities of higher education organizations is within the competence of state bodies. In particular, we are talking about the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (hereinafter - MSHE), which is a state body that exercises leadership in the field of higher and postgraduate education, language policy, science, quality assurance in science, higher and postgraduate education, digitalization of science, higher and postgraduate education.

The main tasks of the MSHE include:

1) the formation and implementation of a unified state policy, the implementation of inter-sectoral coordination in the field of higher and postgraduate education, scientific and scientific-technical activities, the commercialization of the results of scientific and (or) scientific-technical activities, as well as in the field of language development, *the development and implementation of international programs in the field of higher and postgraduate education and science;*

2) creation of necessary conditions for obtaining higher and (or) postgraduate education;

3) improvement of the organization of scientific research and increase of its competitiveness;

4) creation of conditions for commercialization of results of scientific and (or) scientific and technical activity.

Among the key functions of the MSHE are: conducting negotiations with foreign partners and signing, within its competence, *international treaties (agreements) and programs* in the field of higher and (or) postgraduate education, as well as scientific activities; developing and approving rules for organizing *international cooperation* carried out by organizations of higher and (or) postgraduate education, and coordinating this work; implementing *international cooperation* in the field of science; implementing obligations under scientific and scientific-technical programs and projects stipulated by *international treaties* of the Republic of Kazakhstan [15].

International scholarship of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan “Bolashaq”.

A unique Kazakhstani program for training highly qualified specialists abroad opens up a large layer of opportunities for establishing and developing mutually beneficial partnerships. In the context of the transition of the economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan to market relations, the expansion of international relations, an urgent need has arisen for personnel with the appropriate education, in connection with which it is becoming especially relevant to send the most prepared young people to study in leading educational institutions of foreign countries. In order to create financial support for this activity, select candidates and coordinate international relations in the field of education, it was decided to establish the international scholarship of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan “Bolashaq” for the education of talented youth in leading educational institutions of the USA, Great Britain, France, Germany and other countries [16].

The “Bolashaq” scholarship is personal and is awarded by the Republican Commission in accordance with the list of priority specialties for the purposes of:

1) full-time education of citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan to obtain master's degrees, doctor of philosophy (PhD), doctor of science in their field, residency training *in leading foreign higher education institutions included in the list of leading foreign higher education institutions, foreign organizations recommended for training, language courses for winners of the competition*, approved at the time of participation in the competition or in subsequent years;

2) internships by categories of workers determined by the Republican Commission, from among citizens of the Republic of Kazakhstan for a period of up to 12 (twelve) months in foreign organizations based *on leading foreign higher education institutions included in the list of leading foreign higher education institutions, foreign organizations recommended for training, language courses by competition winners, as well as recognized global research centers, scientific organizations within the framework of research campaigns, industry organizations and in production.*

The list of leading foreign higher education institutions, foreign organizations recommended for training, language courses for the winners of the competition, as well as the list of priority specialties are approved by the working body [17].

According to official statistics, 1,137 applicants were admitted to the competition for the “Bolashaq” international scholarship in 2023. Based on the results of 4 meetings of the Republican Commission for Personnel Training Abroad during the reporting period, the “Bolashaq” international scholarship was awarded to 550 applicants:

- under the Master's program - 418 people;
- under the Doctoral program - 19 people;
- under the Internship program - 113 people [18].

Conclusion. Higher education institutions have a great responsibility to form future sustainability leaders and support the ambitious Sustainable Development Goals targets implementation. Sustainability is also an essential aspect of a university's reputation and prestige globally. Higher education establishes the mindset of adult people and is considered a “changing agents” towards sustainability development. Nevertheless, the geography of mindset change is not equal, and not all have equal access to higher education [19].

Thus, the conducted research of international and national legal frameworks for establishing partnerships and relationships between stakeholders in the field of higher education showed:

1. The international legal basis for establishing cooperation can be conditionally divided into basic norms that guarantee a person's right to education, and special norms aimed at establishing contractual relations between interested parties.

2. Stakeholders may include persons responsible for the implementation of international legal standards in the field of higher education at the national and institutional levels (government bodies; teaching staff, researchers, students; administrative staff; representatives of the public).

3. At the multilateral level of cooperation, one of the striking and successful examples is the creation of a network model of education, when several partner universities unite into a consortium to train specialists within the framework of a “double diploma program” (SU CIS, SCO University).

4. Bilateral international agreements (using the Republic of Kazakhstan as an example) also serve as the basis for establishing partnerships both at the level of states and governments, and at the level of educational institutions (inter-university agreements, etc.). In addition, the subject of such agreements is not only issues of higher education, but also science and the scientific and technical sphere.

5. The national legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the Basic Law of the country guarantees the right of every person to education. In addition to this, there are 2 specific laws (“On Education” and “On Science”), which separately establish the rules on the procedure and conditions for establishing international cooperation. In addition, at the subordinate level, the competence of the authorized state body in the field of higher education and science in terms of coordinating international cooperation of the state body itself and higher education organizations accountable to it is prescribed.

6. The phenomenon of Kazakhstani education is the International Scholarship “Bolashak”, which has

become famous throughout the world. Such a program is built exclusively on the basis of foreign partnership with leading universities of the world and is aimed at training Kazakhstani specialists abroad.

7. An important aspect is the possibility of conducting public control, when citizens of Kazakhstan, individually or as part of a group, as well as non-profit organizations, have the right to analyze and evaluate acts and decisions of autonomous educational organizations for compliance with public interests.

Taking into account the conducted research and the conclusions presented, the *following recommendations are available:*

- despite the large number of concluded international treaties and agreements, the question of the need to conduct an appropriate audit regarding their validity or extension nevertheless remains;

- by analogy with the projects “CIS Network University” and “SCO University”, it is recommended to continue the practice of creating new international programs using the example of Kazakhstan's participation in regional integration associations (CICA, etc.);

- MSHE and partner universities participating in double-degree programs should develop and implement standard joint educational programs (curricula) in order to avoid discrepancies and further problems with the mutual crediting of mastered disciplines;

- within the framework of the International Scholarship “Bolashaq”, strengthen measures to control and return Kazakhstani citizens to the Republic of Kazakhstan upon completion of their studies abroad;

- expand the list of objects of public control by adding higher and postgraduate education organizations.

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